

PROBLEMS OF GENDER LINGUISTICS

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Annotation.

This paper deals with the information about the problems of gender linguistic. It also discusses the differences between men's and women's speech, adult's and adolescent's speech, boy's and girl's speech.

Keywords.

gender, linguistics, sociolinguistics, pragmatics, sociolinguistic, psycholinguistic.

Development of linguistics in the 20th century and important trends in the 21st century such as sociolinguistics, psycholinguistics, computational linguistics, cognitive linguistics. It is not for nothing that bordering areas are defined, because these areas directly affect the language learns in connection with practice. This takes linguistics to another level along with raising, to further clarify the ideas about the language, its structure to a deeper analysis, the development of language, psychological and physiological processes in a person helps clarify issues such as the importance of language.

Recently, the mass media, in particular, on the pages of our press publicist reports on gender relations have increased significantly. Especially, Considerations aimed at increasing the role of women in society are very important. These are the most serious results achieved in socio-psychological research before that it turns out to be related to the concept of gender to one degree or another. As long as it's in our language After that, gender, i.e., the term "gender" begins to take an active part, its sociolinguistic it is necessary to clarify its content as a concept.

V.A. Kirilina¹⁰ conducted research on the current gender problem two divides into directions:

¹⁰ See: Kirilina A.V. Issledovanie gendera v lingvisticheskikh nauchnyx distsiplinax// Gendernye education and system of higher and secondary schools: condition and perspective: material international scientific conference, Ivanovo, June 24-25, 2003. - Ivanovo: Ivan.gost.un-t, 2003. - pp. pp. 132-138.

1. Gender problem in humanities. In sociology, psychology the studied research is the basis for linguistics. Gender as a category and anthropological status is studied.

a) The general principles of gender analysis:

- The gender is a product of culture and social development and has a comparative character. It is also recognized as a conventional essence.
- The gender is variable like other sociocultural constructs.
- The gender is a universal category; the uniqueness of gender within each discipline and it is necessary to take into account which methods are used to study.

b) The linguistic principles of gender analysis:

- The gender is considered an important criterion of communicative dialogue.
- The cultural symbolic nature of gender gives rise to analogies related to gender causes to come.

• The linguistic methods for studying gender aspects of language and communication is used. Generally (sociolinguistic, psycholinguistic, linguistic and cultural studies and other) methods are used in linguistics.

2. Linguistic genderology or the problem of gender linguistics. Gender Linguistics included in scientific gender research learns gender with the help of linguistic concepts.

In addition, linguistic genderology is as unique as any new direction to the edges, that is, it is a new direction in which the categories of the apparatus of concepts are not clearly formed. This new direction is in the process of forming its own research methods and methods. At the same time, scientists in the scientific field of linguistics from the methods of linguistic research and sociolinguistics, psycholinguistics and other humanities (linguistics, history, literary studies, etc.) methods are used.

The development of gender linguistics is the development of modern philosophy and of the 20th century in connection with the exchange of scientific directions of humanities corresponds to the last 10 years. The gender linguistics generally has two groups explores the questions:

1. The appearance of gender in language: lexicon, syntax, rod category and line

appears in sections. The purpose of this approach is to express the language of people of different genders, how men and women are valued and which the fact that they are more common in semantic areas, what is the basis of this linguistic is represented by the presence of a mechanism.

2. The emergence of gender in speech: what are the tools and contexts of gender expressed by means of social factors and communicative tools to this process the effect is studied. So far, social in this area the theory of determinism and the theories of bio determinism have been competing.

Nowadays, various aspects of gender are studied in gender linguistics.

We found it is necessary to highlight some of them:

- gender and intonation;
- gender and accent;
- gender and gemination;
- gender and lexical layer;
- gender and meaning shift;
- gender and morphological indicators;
- gender and syntactic means;
- gender and phraseology;
- gender and discourse;
- gender and pragmatics;
- gender and the linguistic landscape of the world;
- gender and virtual communication;
- gender and paralinguistic tools, etc.

The gender is a multifaceted concept. Therefore, it is related to gender problems are the object of examination of many fields. In particular gender is being researched in various aspects of in such as linguistics, psychology, sociology, cognitology.

The gender differences in the construction of language provide its key and mechanism. The analysis of gender language refers to a number of directions:

a) sociolinguistics is the social nature of language, its social function, the social nature of language explores a number of issues such as the influence of factors, the role of language policy in language development¹¹;

b) psycholinguistics is the mechanism of the emergence of speech, children's speech studies issues such as the process of formation, information transfer function of speech¹²;

c) ethnolinguistics is the language belongs to the ethnic culture of the owner of this language relationship, ethnoculture in the process of language functioning and development, studies the relationship between ethnopsychological factors¹³;

¹¹ A. Nurmonov, B. Yoldoshev. Linguistics and natural sciences. - T. "Sharq", 2001, p. 70.

¹² That work. Page 68.

¹³ A. Nurmonov, Sh. Iskandarov. Linguistic theory. - t., "Science", 2008, p. 158.

d) neurolinguistics is a product of the brain, the brain studies issues such as the impact of illness on the speech activity¹⁴;

e) metalinguistics learns the parts of the objective world between the attitude of linguistic representations¹⁵.

So, the gender linguistics will appear at the intersection of the above-mentioned disciplines sciences in the field. The gender linguistics is now a topic in Uzbek linguistics. It is one of the emerging fields of science, which uses linguistic concepts to define gender learns.

Speech of adults and adolescents, women's and men's speech, boys' and girls' speech, with emphasis on children's speech differences in gender attitudes in children's speech, artistic works; social roles, division of forms of activity, behavior and psychological descriptions of individuals differences are implied in scientific research in the field of gender linguistics speech.

One of the current problems of gender linguistics is gender relations pragmatic simile, pragmatic is the study of phenomena such as conflict. Because men and women have a different pragmatic world.

In the emergence of men's and women's speech, their psychological characteristics, age, profession, social background and family environment are of particular importance. In this respect defining the direction of neurolinguistic research within the framework of gender linguistics is the current period is an urgent problem of linguistics.

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¹⁴ That work. Page 165

¹⁵ That work. Page 164.

7. Chrestomathy of the course of the basics of gender research. -T. "Uzbekistan".

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